

IP CAMERA A TOOL FOR EFFECTIVE SURVEILLANCE SYSTEM

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Abstract

IP surveillance is an important part of every modern security system which augments the protection of assets, homes and industrial facilities. Over the past decades, it has become part of internet of things (IoT). As the names implies, IP surveillance is a network solution where each camera is made up of its own IP address and password. This solution offers several advantages because it is built on a network; it is scalable and offers flexible installation and placement. It uses cost effective cat 6 cabling, which carries power, video, audio, PTZ (Plan, Tilt, Zoom) and event data. Remote viewing and management is integrated. This article explains the role of IP cameras in effective surveillance systems.

INTRODUCTION

Technology is part of our daily lives; we have become accustomed to it that we are confident in its security and privacy. A typical example is the surveillance system which has prevented many miscreants' intrusion into our system almost in all facets of our world.

Surveillance cameras are video cameras used for the purpose of observing an area. They are often connected to a recording device or IP network, and may be watched by a security guard or law enforcement officer. Cameras and recording equipment used to be relatively expensive and required human personnel to monitor camera footage, but analysis of footage has been made easier by automated software that

organizes digital video footage into a searchable database, and by video analysis software.

In response to the demands for quick, efficient and reliable services, industry players are increasingly deploying technology as a means of generating insights into customers' behavioural patterns and preferences. Well developed outsourcing support functions (technology and operations) are increasingly being used to provide services and manage costs

Presently, IP cameras with network interfaces have become widely available from an increasing number of manufacturers, with high definition image quality and sophisticated camera functionalities. These cameras are directly attached to a data network, such as a local or wide area network from where the camera is then directly accessed and viewed from a computer on the network.

Building block of an IP Camera

However, there is a serious setback with the use of IP cameras in surveillance of systems, despite its wide use; there is every tendency and fear that it will succumb to threats.

IP cameras

There are different types of surveillance cameras, these types are used for different purposes, and most common among them are the CCTV cameras and the IP cameras. Although IP cameras have enormous characteristics that supersede CCTV cameras, their reliability are not trusted. The table below compares IP cameras characteristics with that of analog systems during video surveillance system performance(Memos et'al, 2018).

Table 1: Compares IP cameras characteristics with that of analog systems

	Scenario with analog cameras	Scenario with IP cameras
Camera resolution	From 420 to 700 TV lines, 4CIF resolution	From 1 Mpixel to 8 MPixel
Cabling (Video and Power)	Coaxial to each camera and DVR, additional power cables	Cat 5e, Power over Ethernet (PoE)
The average cable length	100 m/camera (video) 65 m/camera (Power)	65 m/camera (Cat5 with(PoE))
Power	Power for Cameras	PoE
Switches	To all types DVR	PoE switch
Server / memory	Mid-end DVR (H.264 compatible with memory)	PC (standard) with memory
Software	On the DVR (H.264 compatible)	AxIS Camera Station
Monitor	Standard high resolution monitors	Standard high resolution monitors

CCTV cameras are preferred to IP cameras because of the belief that IP cameras may at times be threatened and used by fraudsters as a spy. With the advancement in technology, IP cameras have dominated because of their complex benefits, which transform the video signals inside the cameras into a digital form, in contrast to the older types of cameras (Alshalawi & Alghamdi, 2017)(Gradimirka et'al, 2013).

The IP camera is resident on the local area network (LAN). Video data is transmitted through the LAN to a video server that routes the videos to end users and mass storage server.

PROS AND CONS

IP cameras are the least secure CCTV system, but may have application where remote viewing over a network is desired or where a high bandwidth network exists. With an IP camera system, a network connection between the sites is all that is required to view any camera image on the system. However, they cost more than a standard analogue non IP camera.

Overview of IP surveillance system

An IP surveillance system can be simple or complicated, depending on the need. A simple scenario when one wants to view and record video will be connecting a personal computer to an Ethernet cable and then to network switch which allows different devices to be connected also and a cable from the switch is connected to the camera location. Then equipment that can capture video and send stream over network is needed, which is a network camera or an analog camera connected to a video encoder, this is sometimes known as a video server. Below is a diagram showing an overview of an IP surveillance system.

Overview of IP surveillance system

IP video Surveillance Systems

IP Surveillance refers to a security system that presents a user the ability to monitor and record video/audio over an Internet Protocol based computer network such as a local area network or the internet (IP Surveillance Design Guide, 2008). IP Surveillance sometimes also known as network video or IP CCTV uses the IP Network technology as the backbone for transporting information.

Conclusion

IP cameras are susceptible to attacks, although they have many characteristics. As a result of these characteristics and with the growth in technology, IP cameras are widely used.

As a result of the digital nature and method of video distribution, IP based surveillance systems introduce a host of advanced functionalities that enhance greater control and management of live and recorded video data

thereby making them highly suitable for security surveillance applications. Some of these include remote accessibility, high image quality, easy and future proof integration, scalability, flexibility, cost effectiveness, event management and intelligent video

References

Alshalawi R. & Alghamdi T. "*Forensic tool for wireless surveillance camera*", 2017 19th International Conference on Advanced Communication Technology (ICACT), 2017.

Memos V., Psannis K., Ishibashi Y., Kim B. & Gupta B., "*An Efficient Algorithm for Media-based Surveillance System (EAMSuS) in IoT Smart City Framework*", *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 83, pp. 619-628, 2018.

Gradimirka P., Nebojsa A. , Branimir J., Boris G., Mile P., "*Overview, Characteristics and Advantages of IP Camera Video Surveillance Systems Compared to Systems with other Kinds of Camera*", *International Journal of Engineering Science and Innovative Technology (IJESIT)*, vol. 2, no. 5, 2013.

Harold F., "Official Guide to Certified information system security professionals CBK" December 2009, ISBN: 1439801607, 9781439809600. Second Edition.